

Marine LitterWatch

Marine LitterWatch is a citizen science project that tackles the problem of marine litter.

The main **objective** of the project is filling data gaps on marine litter for EU marine environmental policy (the marine Strategy Framework Directive), involving citizens in its collection and monitoring.

What does it consist of?

To combat the plastic litter problem, communities collect litter from beaches and send data on the items found to the EEA.

Climate Action. How is the project contributing?

- Preserving and enhancing marine resilience, especially for vulnerable habitats, is crucial in combating climate change and human impacts.
- The lack of long-term data often undermines confidence in resilience assessments.
- Integrating climate change and marine litter into resilience frameworks enables more effective actions to be implemented (Lincoln et al. 2022)

Requirements

- Participants should be familiar with the diversity of marine litter items. Even so, the project applications inform on the typologies of litter items.
- Digital tools, like a mobile app or access to the website to submit the survey with the observations are recommended.
- Gloves, boots, and bags to collect the litter are recommended.

Language English

Place Global

Citizen's involvement	☆☆☆☆☆
Equitable use	☆☆☆☆☆
Flexibility in use	☆☆☆☆☆
Simple and intuitive use	☆☆☆☆☆
Clear content	☆☆☆☆☆
Perceptible Information	☆☆☆☆☆
Tolerance for Error	☆☆☆☆☆

environmental health
marine litter

Information of Marine LitterWatch

<https://marinelitterwatch.discomap.eea.europa.eu/>

Similar projects

Marina Conservative Society – <https://www.mcsuk.org/>

Developed by:

The [European Environment Agency](#) (EEA) has developed **Marine LitterWatch** to strengthen Europe's knowledge base and thus provide support to European policy making.

Activities to carry out during the assembly

Organization

- ❑ **Detecting ongoing citizen science activities within the community** by identify organizations, researchers, or communities engaged in relevant actions, such as Marine LitterWatch, to include them in the regular programme.
- ❑ **Addressing citizen concerns** through the identification of existing citizen science projects, like Marine LitterWatch, to pinpoint areas most impacted by litter, thus addressing community concerns effectively.

Learning

- ❑ **Invite citizen scientist testimonials and deploy citizen science actions** using Marine LitterWater. It can inspire, empower, engage and foster participation of the assembly, while enriching knowledge and experience uptaking in a bottom-up manner.

- ❑ **Facilitate knowledge sharing through presentations** of previous research, citizen science workshops, testimonials, or collective actions, such as litter sampling or data collection during the assembly.
- ❑ **Offer visual representations of data** collected through MLW to enhance understanding and accessibility of citizen science findings and perform an activity around the visuals.
- ❑ **Integrating citizen science projects into public spaces** during assemblies. Encourage public institutions like libraries or schools to integrate related to the climate topics discussed in the assembly and incorporate their insights into the assembly using Marine LitterWater.

Recommendation

- ❑ **Utilizing outcomes of citizen science projects for policymaking and expert guidance.** Incorporate recommendations from Marine LitterWater, which are based on evidence collected by citizen scientists, into policy decisions and expert assessments [1-3].

Follow-up

- ❑ **Establishing citizen observatories to monitor the effectiveness of public measures.** Enable citizens to monitor the impact of public measures, such as litter control efforts on coastlines, through citizen observatories previously stablished or created ad-hoc in the last phase of the assembly.
- ❑ **Providing updates on policy implementation.** Inform assembly participants about policy implementation progress and monitor changes in litter levels to assess the effectiveness of implemented measures, particularly in coastal areas.

Who can used?

[Organizers]

[Experts]

[Civil society]

[Citizens]

[1] [From source to sea — The untold story of marine litter](#)

[2] [Outlook and recommendations](#)

[3] [ETC/ICM Report 5/2022: Marine Litter in Europe - An integrated assessment from source to sea](#)